

SUSTAINABLE COMPOSITES START WITH LCA: SEEING THE WHOLE PICTURE

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ABSTRACT

The increasing urgency to address environmental challenges and reduce the environmental footprint of industrial processes has led to significant interest in the development of sustainable composite materials, commonly referred to as green composites or biocomposites. These materials usually consist of a bio-based or biodegradable polymer matrix reinforced with natural fibers.

In principle, biocomposites combine environmental benefits — such as reduced greenhouse gas emissions, lower energy consumption and better disposal options — with promising mechanical properties and low weight.

However, the concept of "sustainability" in the context of green composites is multidimensional and encompasses not only the origin of the material and biodegradability, but also metrics of life cycle assessment, durability, resource renewability and socio-economic impact. A holistic assessment of these aspects is essential to avoid the risk of greenwashing and to ensure the true environmental benefits of these new materials.

In this work, a representative case study from the literature is presented to highlight the importance of critically assessing the environmental impact of supposedly green materials such as biocomposites. The aim is to emphasize the crucial role of LCA analysis as an additional tool to characterize newly proposed materials.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the transition to sustainable materials and production systems has become an urgent global priority. This change is driven by the growing awareness of environmental degradation, climate change, resource depletion and the unsustainable nature of many conventional production processes. In this context, green composites and especially biocomposites have emerged as one of the most promising material families to support a circular economy with low environmental impact. In the broadest sense, biocomposites are composite materials in which either the matrix, the reinforcement or both are derived from renewable, natural or biodegradable sources [1].

Biocomposites usually consist of natural fibers (such as flax, jute, hemp, sisal or agricultural residues) embedded in a polymer matrix that is either biodegradable (e.g. PLA, PHB) or bio-based (e.g. bio-polyethylene, bio-epoxy resins). These materials represent an attractive and increasingly feasible alternative to conventional composite materials based on synthetic fibers and petroleum-based resins. Their attractiveness lies not only in their use of renewable raw materials, but also in their potential to lower carbon emissions, reduce energy consumption during manufacture and improve end-of-life options, including composting and recyclability [2,3].

The environmental motivation for the development of biocomposites stems from their potential to mitigate various impacts associated with conventional composites. For example, life cycle assessment (LCA) studies have shown that natural fibers can reduce the global warming potential (GWP) of composites by 20–50% compared to synthetic alternatives [4]. This is mainly due to carbon sequestration during plant growth and the lower embodied energy of natural fibers. In addition, many bio-based polymers are derived from agricultural waste streams or non-food biomass, which underlines their sustainability and reduces competition with food resources.

Economically, biocomposites offer the opportunity to utilize local biomass resources, especially in rural or developing regions, thus promoting green value chains and decentralized production systems. The growing market demand for sustainable solutions, particularly in the automotive, packaging, consumer goods and construction industries, has created further incentives for research and innovation in this area.

Despite these advantages, the development and introduction of green composites still faces a number of technical and systemic challenges. First, natural fibers exhibit variations in their mechanical properties due to different growing conditions, harvesting and processing techniques. This inconsistency can affect the predictability and repeatability of composite performance [5]. In addition, natural fibers are hydrophilic, which can lead to poor interfacial bonding with hydrophobic matrices and moisture absorption, reducing long-term durability, especially in humid environments [6].

Another limitation concerns the trade-offs in mechanical properties: while biocomposites are lightweight and often sufficiently strong for semi-structural applications, they may not achieve the stiffness, heat resistance or impact strength of high-performance synthetic composites such as carbon or glass fiber systems. Advanced fiber treatments (e.g. silanization, acetylation) and matrix modifications (e.g. compatibilizers, nanofillers) are currently being explored to address these issues, but they may result in environmental impacts or higher costs, negating some of the original sustainability benefits.

It is crucial to emphasize that sustainability in materials science is not a topic that is limited to a single variable. It must be evaluated through a holistic and multi-criteria lens. While bio-based origin and biodegradability are important, they alone are not enough to claim true environmental sustainability. Factors such as durability, toxicity, ethics in the supply chain, renewal rate and overall life cycle performance must also be considered. Indeed, some bio-based polymers require high energy inputs or generate significant emissions during synthesis, necessitating a careful LCA comparison with petrochemical alternatives [7]. Furthermore, end-of-life scenarios remain a complex issue. While certain biocomposites are marketed as biodegradable, actual degradation rates vary widely depending on conditions, and industrial composting facilities may be required for effective degradation. In parallel, thermoplastic-based biocomposites can be recycled, but the separation of fibers and matrix remains a technical challenge. As a result, many green composites are still incinerated or landfilled unless they are specifically designed for the circular economy [8].

Overall, the future of biocomposites lies in the balance between performance, sustainability and scalability. From a system perspective, there is a growing need for standardization, certification systems and eco-labels that can validate the sustainability claims of green composites. This includes harmonized methods for life cycle assessment, toxicity screening and biodegradability testing. Such frameworks are essential to avoid the pitfalls of greenwashing and to inform both consumers and industrial users about the real benefits and limitations of these materials.

2 CASE STUDY

In a recent review by Suarez et al. the aspects related to sustainability of polymer composites were assessed, with the goal of highlighting if natural-based composites are actually sustainable [9]. The authors concluded that “there is a wide number of publications dealing with the use of natural fibers or natural, biodegradable or biobased matrices, which claims to be producing a more sustainable or more environmentally friendly material than those based on fuel, although very few of them have performed environmental analysis to really demonstrate this point”. Although the number of studies using LCA analyzes to quantify the environmental impact of biocomposites together with their technical performance is increasing, much remains to be done to understand the relationship between materials, processing and performance, both in terms of final application and environmental impact. As a representative case study in this direction, the work done by Filippone and co-workers [10] is considered in the following. In particular, the environmental implications due to the presence of the lignocellulosic microfibers were assessed by using unfilled PLA as benchmark. A “cradle-to-gate” life cycle analysis was carried out, considering the following three processes: a) production of the microfibers; b) production of the PLA; c) manufacturing of the bio-pellets (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: System boundary (*cradle-to-gate* life cycle). The process is divided into three sub-processes: a) production of the microfibers; b) production of the PLA; c) manufacturing of the bio-pellets. Taken from [10].

Moreover, since the origin of natural fibers has a strong effect on their environmental impact, two types of fibers are considered in the study, namely kenaf and pine needles microfibers, in order to compare cultivated and naturally grown feedstocks. Original fibers and microfibers obtained after the grinding process are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Pine needles and kenaf fibers before (a, c) and after (b, d) the grinding process. The arrow in a) indicates the fascicle sheath. Magnifications in b) and d) show the microfibers obtained after grinding that were used for producing the green composites. Taken from [10].

Interestingly, the LCA analysis revealed that fibers obtained from naturally grown raw material are only slightly better than cultivated ones in terms of environmental impacts. The main advantages of using natural raw materials concern the indicators for human toxicity and ecotoxicity. This is mainly

due to the impact of the washing and drying phases of the pine needles. Greater advantages of naturally grown raw materials are expected in the event of an industrial scale-up of fiber production. More importantly, the environmental impact of composites resulting from the combination of the effects of polymer and fillers and the contribution of the melt mixing process is much lower than that of pure PLA. The higher the fiber content, the greater the benefits (Fig. 3). The reason for this is that the fibers represent a negligible environmental impact compared to the polymer matrix. Therefore, replacing “high impact” PLA with “low impact” natural fibers is always preferable.

Figure 3: Percentage change in the environmental impacts of x PN and x KB bio-pellets with respect to pure PLA pellets (x indicates the percentage volume fraction of microfibers in the composite). Taken from [10].

In addition to the benefits arising from the improved environmental fingerprint, the selected fibers are also expected to improve the performance of the tested materials to a certain extent. This has an indirect impact on the overall sustainability of the composites, as improved performance potentially enables material savings [11]. For this reason, the mechanical performance of the composite samples was estimated and converted into weight reductions (Fig. 4).

A stiffness-limited design of a panel proves that the use of green composites instead of pure PLA leads to material savings of up to 8% (at 30% of the KB). By optimizing the formulation, e.g. by using surface-treated natural fibers to improve the polymer-fiber interaction, a much greater weight reduction could be achieved. In the latter case, a functionality-based LCA would be also necessary to assess whether this material saving outweighs the environmental impact of the fiber treatment.

Figure 4: a) Flexural modulus of green composite samples as function of the fiber content. The testing setup for 3-point bending measurements is shown in the inset (dashed lines are guides for the eye). b) Percentage weight reduction achievable using green composites at different fiber content to realize a rectangular panel at fixed bending stiffness. Taken from [10].

3 CONCLUSIONS

In summary, green composites are a rapidly developing area with great potential to support the transition to sustainable and circular material systems. Their environmental attractiveness is obvious, but scientific rigor and holistic assessment are essential to ensure that their development leads to real environmental and social benefits. Collaboration between materials scientists, environmental engineers, industrial designers and policy makers will be crucial to overcome the current barriers and make biocomposites mainstream across all industries.

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